

TEST STRATEGY AND DATA REDUCTION METHOD
FOR THE THICK ADHEREND TEST PROCEDURE

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ABSTRACT

A test strategy and data reduction method were developed and validated for the thick adherend test procedure. This standard test is used to obtain load-deflection curves for high-strength adhesive systems from which design and analysis data can be derived. However, a finite element analysis has shown that a significant portion of the measured deflection is due to strain in the adherend, especially at cryogenic temperatures. A data reduction method is presented which removes the adherend deflection by comparing load-deflection data from two or more tests with different bond-line thicknesses or measuring device locations.

The data reduction method contains a simple theory which linearly relates the measured deflection to the adhesive bondline thickness and to the distance of the measuring device from the bondline. Using finite element analysis, the linearity of these relations is checked and found to be good for thicker bondlines and small measuring device offsets. Examination of different bondline and offset combinations suggests the best test strategy is to use two or more bondline thicknesses for the same adhesive, with the measuring devices located as close to the bondline as possible.

The results of adhesive test programs which apply this strategy are presented. For room temperature tests, the method is shown to work very well. For cryogenic tests, the expected pattern is evident, but experimental scatter due to the very small deflections is significant.

KEYWORDS: Adhesives; Test Method; Cryogenic; Finite Element Analysis; Joint, Bonded;

1. INTRODUCTION

The characterization of adhesive material systems at cryogenic temperatures has become increasingly relevant recently with the application of composite materials to aerospace and superconducting magnet structures. Analysis methods such as Hart-Smith's A4EI (1) for bonded joints in these and other structures require accurate adhesive properties such as shear modulus, proportional limit stress and ultimate shear strength to be found. These are obtained from standard procedures such as the thick adherend test or the torsional ring test.

An important parameter in the performance of bonded joints is the initial shear stiffness, especially when two materials with different coefficients of thermal expansion are being joined. This is derived from the slope of the linear portion of the adhesive's shear stress-strain curve, which typically tend to be highly nonlinear at room temperature but remain linear until close to failure at cryogenic temperatures.

One of the more economical methods for obtaining a shear stress-strain curve is the thick adherend test procedure. This test provides a load-deflection curve from which the shear stress-strain curve can be derived. Its accuracy and reliability have often been questioned, for example by Renton (2), and Rix and Eastland (3) presented initial findings from a finite element analysis of a thick adherend test specimen which showed that adherend deflection was a significant part of the total measured deflection. This was especially true at cryogenic temperatures where the shear deflections are very small due to the reduced ductility of the adhesive. This paper presents a test strategy and data reduction method for the thick adherend test which helps to minimize the effect of the adherend deflection and improve the accuracy of the measured data.

2. THICK ADHEREND TEST ANALYSIS

2.1 Description of Thick Adherend Tensile Shear Test

The thick adherend test is a tensile symmetric single lap shear test which uses thick rigid plates to minimize the out-of-plane bending (see Figure 1). This in theory loads the adhesive in pure shear without the influence of excessive peel stresses. The shear deflection in the adhesive is measured by obtaining the relative displacement of the adherends across the adhesive bondline. However, the bondlines are so thin that placing the measuring devices directly on the adhesive is not possible and they have to be placed a finite distance from the bondline. This introduces an error in the measured deflection because it contains a combination of adhesive and adherend deflections (see Figure 2). The ratio of adhesive to adherend deflection is a function of gauge location, bond line thickness, adherend moduli, adhesive ductility, and load levels.

Preliminary testing at General Dynamics using aluminum adherends and modified epoxy adhesives indicated that the deformation in the adherends was a significant portion of the total

deflection measured and could not be neglected in calculating adhesive shear strains. In order to determine the magnitude of this problem, an extensive analysis of the thick adherend test specimen was conducted to determine stresses, strains, and deformations in the test specimen. A summary of the results of this analysis, which are presented in more detail in Reference 3, is given below.

12.7 mm Al 2024-T3 Adherends
(0.50")

Figure 1. Thick Adherend Test Specimen.

Figure 2. Thick Adherend Test Output.

Figure 3. Thick Adherend Test Assembly.

2.2 Finite Element Analysis of Thick Adherend Test Specimen

The nonlinear finite element analysis of the thick adherend test specimen was conducted using MSC/NASTRAN. Two models were built to the dimensions shown in Figure 1 with bondline thicknesses of 0.127 mm (.005") and 0.254 mm (.010"). The nonlinear stress-strain curves for American Cyanamid's FM 300-1K modified epoxy adhesive system were input at three temperatures (-55°C, 24°C, and 126°C). A uniform tensile load was applied in steps up to the failure load of the adhesive. The absolute displacements of points either side of the bondline corresponding to the location of the clamping screws on the measuring device (see Figure 3) were recorded. The difference between these displacements represents the shear deflection in the adhesive as the measuring device on the thick adherend test specimen would record it.

The load-deflection curves derived in this way were compared with the true adhesive load-deflection curve derived from the input material properties. Figure 4 shows the comparison for a case with a 0.127 mm (.005") bondline thickness, pick-up points located 1.6 mm (.063")

from the bondline, and material properties at 24 °C. It can be seen that the difference is significant, especially in the linear part of the curve, and this can be attributed to deflection in the adherend being included in the "measured" deflection.

The significance of the adherend deflection as a percentage of the measured deflection was found to increase as pick-up points were taken further away from the bondline. At -55°C, the adhesive stays linear to failure, so the adherend deflections were found to be significant at every load level. The analysis showed however that there was very little difference between adherend deflections for the two models with different bondline thicknesses at the same load level, especially close to the bondline. In order to minimize the errors in the measured data, the following data reduction method was proposed.

Figure 4. Load-deflection Curves for FM 300-1K at 24° C Derived from Finite Element Analysis of Thick adherend Test Specimen.

3. DATA REDUCTION METHOD

A method of accounting for the adherend deflection was developed which involves conducting multiple tests using adhesive bond lines of different thicknesses. By using assumptions of linearity, it was possible to separate the adherend deflection from the measured deflection to leave the true adhesive deflection.

3.1 Assumptions of the Data Reduction Method

The deflection measured by the clip gauges includes some adherend deflection which may be significant:

$$\text{Measured Deflection (d)} = \text{Adhesive Deflection (d}_a\text{)} + \text{Adherend Deflection (d}_m\text{)}$$

Two of the parameters that influence the deflection measured in the thick adherend test are the thickness of the adhesive bondline and the distance of the clamping screws on the measuring device from the bondline. Assuming that the adhesive is in pure shear and that the shear is uniform across the bondline, the adhesive deflection is directly proportional to the thickness of the bondline:

$$\text{Adhesive Deflection (d}_a\text{)} = \text{Shear Strain } (\gamma) \times \text{Bondline Thickness (t)}$$

The adherend deflection is governed by the distance of the measuring device from the bondline. The finite element analysis showed that it becomes greater as this distance increases. Therefore the closer the clamping screws are placed to the bondline, the less significant the adherend deflection will be. It also showed that for different bondline thicknesses, the deflection in the adherend is the same for the same load. So if the same measuring device is used for every test and placed at the same point every time, the adherend deflection can be removed by using test specimens with different bondline thicknesses and the following equations.

For two tests at the same load level with different bondline thicknesses:

$$d_1 = \gamma t_1 + d_m$$

$$d_2 = \gamma t_2 + d_m$$

Subtracting one measured deflection from the other eliminates the adherend deflection, leaving:

$$\gamma = \frac{(d_2 - d_1)}{(t_2 - t_1)}$$

This is the true shear strain in the adhesive, which is assumed to be the same for both bondline thicknesses. Using the shear stress in the adhesive (τ), the shear stiffness G in the linear part of the curve can then be found from:

$$G = \frac{\tau}{\gamma}$$

With this strategy of testing two specimens with different bondline thicknesses, the adherend deflection can be removed and more accurate adhesive data obtained.

3.2 Application to Finite Element Analysis Data

This theory was evaluated initially using data derived from the finite element models. The data reduction method was applied to load-deflection curves obtained from the analyses with

bondline thicknesses of 0.127 mm (.005") and 0.254 mm (.010"), pick-up points at 1.6 mm (.063") from the bondline, and material properties at 24°C. The result was a corrected shear stress-strain curve which is shown in Figure 5. It can be seen that it lies closer to the original material curve than either of the two uncorrected curves. The adherend strain has thus been removed to leave a shear stress-strain curve which represents accurately the true adhesive properties.

Figure 5. Application of Data Reduction Method to Shear Stress-Strain Curves for FM 300-1K at 24° C Derived from Finite Element Analysis of Thick Adherend Test Specimen.

3.3 Application to Test Data

A test program was conducted using the techniques discussed above. A modified epoxy adhesive (Hysol EA 9394) was tested at 24°C (75°F) and in liquid hydrogen at -252°C (-423°F) using aluminum adherends. Two sets of five replicates were tested at each temperature, one set with a nominal bondline thickness of 0.254 mm (.010"), the other with a nominal bondline thickness of 0.508 mm (.020"). These thicknesses were chosen to ensure that the adhesive deflections were large enough to be measurable. The actual average bondline thicknesses were 0.411 mm (.0162") and 0.584 mm (.0230") for the 24°C tests and 0.414 mm (.0163") and 0.600 mm (.0236") for the -252°C tests. The same clip gauge measuring devices were used for all the tests, with the clamping screws placed 1.59 mm (.063") from the bondline, which was the closest that was practically possible.

The room temperature data (24°C) showed close grouping with a clear distinction between the load-deflection curves for the two bondline thicknesses (see Figure 6). The average curves were taken from three of the five replicates after discarding the high and low readings. The coefficient of variation was not more than 8% for any of the load levels. The shear stress-strain data shown in Figure 7 was produced by dividing the load by the shear area and the deflection by the bondline thickness. The fact that all the points lie close to the same curve supports the assumption that shear strain is independent of bondline thickness. When the data reduction method was applied to this data, the result was a shear stress-strain curve that overlapped the average curve, especially in the linear portion. The very small amount of variation around the average curve suggests that the adherend deflection is not in fact significant in this case. The negative adherend deflection implied by the corrected curve being more ductile at higher loads is believed to be due to experimental scatter.

The cryogenic data (-252°C) showed considerably more scatter due primarily to the very small deflections being measured (see Figure 8). The deflections are at the lower limit of the measuring capabilities of the deflection gauges so experimental scatter would be expected. There is still a distinction however between the average load-deflection curves for the two bondline thicknesses, and the expected trend of staying linear to failure is apparent. The shear stress-strain data shows the same scatter, and the corrected curve again implies a negative adherend deflection which can be attributed to the experimental scatter.

These two sets of test data showed much more consistency than previous test programs at General Dynamics which used thinner bondlines and had the measuring devices placed further from the bondline. Good properties for analysis could be generated from the room temperature data with a high degree of confidence. The data reduction method did not reveal conclusive evidence of significant adherend deflections, but by testing with two bondline thicknesses, the reliability of the test data was improved.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The thick adherend tensile lap shear test has been proved to be an economical way of developing design and analysis data for high strength adhesive systems. By using thicker bondlines and placing the measuring devices closer to the bondline, the accuracy and reliability of the adhesive data has been improved. These techniques minimize the errors caused by adherend deflection being included in the measured deflection data.

The adherend deflection can be separated from the measured deflection by testing two sets of specimens with different nominal bondline thicknesses. By recording the data in the same way for every test, the adherend deflection can be removed if it is assumed that it is independent from the bondline thickness. This assumption was backed up by finite element analysis, and test data.

Figure 6. Load-Deflection Test Data for EA9394 at 24° C.

Figure 7. Shear Stress-Strain Test Data for EA9394 at 24° C.

Figure 8. Load-Deflection Test Data for EA9394 at -252° C.

Figure 9. Shear Stress-Strain Test Data for EA9394 at -252° C.

5. REFERENCES

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6. BIOGRAPHY

Chris Eastland received a Bachelor's degree in Engineering Science from Cambridge University in 1986 and an M.S. from the Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics at the University of Washington, Seattle, in 1988. In September 1988, he joined General Dynamics' Space Systems Division as a member of the Advanced Structures Analysis department. His activities have included analysis and design support of pre-design, IRAD and CRAD programs related to aerospace and superconducting magnet structures, specifically in the area of composite materials.

Craig Rix graduated from Iowa State University in 1981 with a B.S. in Civil Engineering. In 1985, he joined General Dynamics and since that time has provided analytical and technical support to IRAD, CRAD, project, and proposal activities. His experience has included coordinating the activities of design, analysis, materials and processes, and manufacturing technology personnel in developing design concepts for aerospace structures. This work has included organizing and conducting test programs to evaluate the behavior of composite materials and structures.

Tom Eisenreich received a M.S. in Engineering Mechanics from the University of Minnesota and a B.S. in Physics and Mathematics from the University of Wisconsin at Eau Claire. He joined General Dynamics in 1983 and is presently coordinator of the Liquid Hydrogen Test Laboratory. He is also currently the principle investigator of several Internal Research and Development (IRAD) programs, which are determining the effects of cryogenic temperatures on the material behavior of composites and adhesives.